

EXPLORING THE PEDAGOGICAL INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL RESOURCES FOR INDIVIDUALIZED ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686555>

Abstract: The article describes digitally assisted individual learning solutions in the English classes. The educational potential of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages in a higher education institution is great. A foreign language is an academic subject that involves the creation of an artificial language environment for students, which predetermines the variable inclusion of various digital learning tools in new prospects for teaching a foreign language.

Keywords: higher education, digital technology, digitalization of education.

Digital learning tools are interactive systems that allow you to simultaneously work with animated computer graphics, sound, video frames, static texts and images. The user, the student, is simultaneously influenced through various information channels, where he, the user, is assigned an active role.

In all the existing and constantly updated diversity, it is necessary to create and update in real time some typology of digital technologies in teaching a foreign language, determine the possibilities of their use and model the methodology for working with them in the conditions of a change in the methodological paradigm. In improving the material base, software and methodological support, in acquiring relevant experience, teachers see the prospect of successful implementation of digitalization of education. [1] A multimedia lesson is a training session using digital technologies, various programs and technical means to effectively influence the student.

All these materials exist, as a rule, in the original version in a foreign language and, therefore, can be used for foreign language classes to develop skills in working with a foreign language as a professional tool.

Training video is a type of Internet resource that allows you to view videos and complete tasks for them, which is used both online and offline. Tasks can be included either in the video itself or in special workbooks. Among the most popular resources are the following:

Digital classroom – among the online resources that help create multimedia lesson plans and deserve mention and implementation in students’ independent and classroom work, one can highlight Google Docs, or Google Docs. This is a free application that simulates MS Office online and includes a text editor, a spreadsheet editor, a service for creating presentations, and a cloud file storage service. Another advantage of the program is that it does not need to be downloaded and installed. Its use ensures communication between the teacher and the student in synchronous and asynchronous mode, allowing you to instantly correct existing shortcomings, misunderstandings or misunderstandings; creation of individual and collective projects independently or under the supervision of a teacher; increasing the volume of tasks solved together with the teacher. [3]

Another online resource is Google Class, which offers free tools for working with email, electronic documents and cloud storage. This service was developed in close collaboration with teachers to save more time so that they can communicate effectively with students. Its advantages are 1) convenient addition of students to the course system; 2) joining students to courses using code and working with several courses simultaneously; 3) creation of advertisements; 4) importing tasks; 4) joint teaching with a large number of colleagues; 5) creating templates and, therefore, reducing the time spent on creating tasks; 6) integration of additional materials (GoogleForms,

PDF files, PPT files and others) from Google Drive. It is also important that this program has a mobile application, which also involves optimizing the work of students. It allows you to highlight text in attached files and tables, add your own notes and comments to them, that is, in fact, conduct an online discussion with teachers. This system also has a number of purely methodological advantages for the teacher, which allows students to develop self-organization skills. The Google Class program has assignment settings options such as 'pre-preparation', 'quick quizzes', 'student assignment tracking', 'individual assignments', using which teachers publish assignments for individual students or the entire course with due dates, change grading system, track graded assignments, transfer final grades to Google Sheets or a CSV file and subsequently send to students, print, etc. [4]

The Padlet service is convenient for organizing, storing materials and collaborating with students. Its unique feature is the similarity of its operating principles with the operating principles of well-known social networks - your page or various materials stored on it can be shared, saved as an electronic document, sent by email, inserted into your page or blog using html code; The service is ideal for working online in a classroom setting, since students can send images and texts to a shared Padlet board from their existing electronic devices and review and discuss them among themselves and with the teacher. Students and the teacher have the opportunity to a) jointly take notes, discuss pressing problems and questions during the lecture online;

The question of choosing methods for conducting training sessions is an everyday one, since specific training situations are very diverse. Cognitive technologies, including information, communication and digital technologies, are tools that help students develop memory and problem-solving skills, and their use changes the nature of the acquisition of knowledge and skills by students, opening up new opportunities for rethinking the content of learning and the effectiveness of methods of its transfer and organizations.

Digital technologies for teaching, monitoring, and demonstration purposes are being integrated into the teaching of various university disciplines, including foreign languages. However, the features of the course, the approaches used by the teacher, the level of requirements for the actual student population must be taken into account; form of training – classroom or distance, synchronous or asynchronous.

Presentations, podcasts, and various tools that help contain as much information as possible in different graphic forms make each lesson on various lexical, grammatical, conversational, and professional topics more vivid, varied and memorable.

Today, all over the world, the ways of teaching foreign languages change daily due to sometimes forced technical and methodological changes in the learning process. The practical mastery of digital tools and materials by teachers and students represents both a reality and a prospect for their successful use in modern education.

Digital learning technologies have enormous learning potential. It is necessary to test in a real educational context their ability to stimulate various types of speech activity and the ability to organize contact and non-contact educational processes in a new way.

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